
Creation of Accessories Shape of Buffalo Head with Source of Ideas for *Unan-Unan* Ceremony Using Waste Techniques

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Abstract

Along with the development of the industrial sector, without realizing it, this raises new problems, namely environmental pollution by liquid, solid, gas, and B3 (Toxic and Hazardous Materials) waste. The purpose of this research is to increase the selling value of waste and manage waste so as not to pollute the environment. This research uses the Practice-led Research method, which is a scientific work derived from ongoing practice research by creating new works through research and practice carried out. On this occasion, the researcher will create an accessory made of styrofoam material and will be published in a Unesa Fashion Creation Title performance in 2023 which carries the big theme of BHUMIBRAMA. The result of this study is an accessory in the shape of a buffalo head with styrofoam as the main material.

Keywords: styrofoam, zero waste, head accessories

Abstrak

Seiring perkembangan sektor industri, tanpa disadari hal tersebut menimbulkan masalah baru yaitu pencemaran lingkungan oleh limbah cair, padat, gas, maupun limbah B3 (Bahan Beracun dan Berbahaya). Tujuan penelitian ini adalah untuk meningkatkan nilai jual dari limbah serta mengelola limbah agar tidak mencemari lingkungan. *Penelitian ini menggunakan metode Practice-led Research* merupakan karya ilmiah yang berasal dari penelitian praktik yang sedang berlangsung dengan menciptakan karya baru melalui riset dan praktik yang dilakukan. Pada kesempatan ini, peneliti akan menciptakan sebuah aksesoris yang terbuat dari bahan *styrofoam* dan akan dipublikasikan dalam sebuah pagelaran Gelar Cipta Busana Unesa

pada tahun 2023 yang mengusung tema besar BHUMIBRAMA. Hasil dari penelitian ini adalah sebuah aksesoris bentuk kepala kerbau dengan bahan utama sterofoam.

Kata kunci: *sterofoam, zero waste, aksesoris kepala*

Introduction

Without realizing it, the development of the world has moved very fast. Various industrial sectors have also developed so that they provide a positive impact on the economy and people's welfare. However, along with the development of the industrial sector, without realizing it, this has caused a new problem, namely environmental pollution by liquid, solid, gas, and B3 (Toxic and Hazardous Materials) waste. Industrial waste that is not properly managed can cause various problems such as damaging ecosystems, causing health problems and interfering with survival. B3 waste is considered the waste that has the most influence on pollution and environmental damage.

The type of waste that is most dangerous to the environment and health is waste that is categorized as B3 (Toxic and Hazardous Materials) waste (Purwanti, 2018). Pollution caused by B3 waste can be through water, tan, and also air. One of the B3 wastes that we often encounter is styrofoam. Styrofoam can be found everywhere such as in industry as well as in household waste. Styrofoam is categorized as B3 waste because it is difficult to decompose in the soil and can cause air pollution if burned. There are several alternatives in managing styrofoam waste, one of which is zero waste.

Fashion products can be in the form of fashion or fashion accessories or accessories. Accessories function as a complement to fashion that can sweeten and support a woman's appearance (Doriza & Putri 2014). Accessories function to add and complement beauty for the wearer in the fashion world (Marcella, 2019) while according to (Doriza & Putri 2014) accessories function as a complement to fashion that can sweeten and support a woman's appearance. (Andalangit, 2021) Accessories are complements that a person wears with a specific function. Accessories are divided into two, namely functional accessories such as shoes, bags, hats and aesthetic accessories such as necklaces, earrings, ring bracelets (Alfiani & Listiani, 2022). (Arumsari, 2015) There are 3 types of accessories, namely Eye wear, Headpiece, Jewelry, and based on their location, accessories are divided into nine, namely, hair and head accessories, ear accessories, neck accessories, hand accessories, finger accessories, leg accessories, waist accessories, eye accessories, and nose accessories. According to (Ni'matul & Lutfiati, 2021) accessories are assessed from several aspects such as design aspects, color aspects, usability aspects, and combination aspects, while according to (A'isyah & Widowati, 2019) it is stated that the assessment criteria for accessories are assessed based on the neatness of the accessories, the shape of the accessories, the strength of the accessories, the design of the accessories, and the final result of the accessories

Styrofoam is very suitable for use as a basic material for making accessories because it is lightweight, flexible and easy to shape. On this occasion, the researcher will create an accessory made of styrofoam material and will be published in a show to show the community that the

waste that we often encounter around us can be processed into new useful products. The fashion show used in the publication media of this work is the Unesa Fashion Creation Title in 2023 which carries the big theme of BHUMIBRAMA. BHUMIBRAMA is inspired by the environment around Mount Bromo, East Java. In this study, zero waste is applied to the use of styrofoam production materials. The material is obtained from the rest of the previous production. Styrofoam obtained from leftovers of production is used as the main skeleton of buffalo head accessories which are then painted using leftover production paint. After the desired frame is formed, then the frame of the accessories is wrapped in ribbons and decorated with beads. By applying the zero waste technique in the manufacture of these accessories, the waste produced will be reduced and can save production costs by reusing leftover production materials. Not only can that, but the application of this technique in the manufacture of accessories also foster creativity to process unused goods into goods with a selling value.

Research Method

The category of creation in this study refers to the issues and problems found in the field and refers to the purpose of the creation. Therefore, in the implementation of this research activity, the researcher must prepare components and elements that are by the goals and benefits of the research. Based on this research, the Practice-led Research method was chosen. According to (Hendriyana, 2022) Practice-led Research is a scientific work that comes from ongoing practice research by creating new works through research and practice.

Bagan 2.1 Kerangka konsep penciptaan

A. Pre-Design

In this study, the accessories that will be made with the zero waste technique choose the source of ideas taken from the tradition of the Unan-Unan ceremony. Researchers need information about the Unan-Unan ceremony, starting from the meaning, purpose, and various offerings used in the ceremony.

Figure 1 *Moodboard* Studio Unan-Unan

1. Source of Idea : Unan-Unan Traditional Ceremony
2. Pallet Color : Black, Grey, Red
3. Fabric : Suede and twill
4. Manipulating fabric: Embroidery and mapping
5. Style : Edgy

B. Creation Planning

1. Designing Works

Alternative Design There are three alternative designs in the selection of accessories. The first design is in the form of a buffalo head horn which is equipped with beads as a depiction of part of the offering in the form of a buffalo head and an offering flower arrangement. The second design, in the form of a deformed buffalo head, is as large as a head. The third design, in the form of a mask of anthropomorphism, is the provision of human attribution to non-human entities, in this case a buffalo head shaped like a human head.

Figure 2 Design alternative

2. Selected Designs

From some of the alternative designs above, the first design was chosen as the design that was considered the most suitable. The first design is considered to match the edgy style of the fashion to be worn in the form of dresses and blazers that tend to be feministic. The accessories are in the form of buffalo horns with beaded ornaments that look like a crown. It is red in line with black clothing with red patterns.

Figure 3 Design digital accessories head of buffalo

3. Working Pictures

A working drawing is a reference that is made to realize an idea towards realization in physical form and must be understandable.

a. Production Design 1

In the first production design, it is explained that the part of the accessories is in the form of a buffalo head-shaped head accessory with its characteristic of two symmetrical horns. Equipped with beads that hang down on each side of the horn as well as on the front and also bare accessories.

Figure 4 Design digital accessories head of buffalo

b. Production Design 2

In this second production stage, it contains an explanation of the parts and also the size of the accessories that will be made with the aim of making it easier to realize the work. The size of these accessories is adjusted to the model's head which has a head circumference of 53 cm, a horn length of 50 cm on each side, and a bead length of 30 cm – 50 cm.

Figure 5 Design digital accessories head of buffalo

4. Model/Master/Prototype

Prototype is the application of the product design to be made, in other words is the initial description of a product to be made. This is done to find out the suitability of the design and the product to be made, so that improvements can be made if there are errors. The prototype in the form of an accessory frame is made with the main material, namely styrofoam. After the results of the prototype are deemed appropriate, it will be continued with the realization stage.

5. Realization

At this stage of realization, buffalo head accessories are made by applying *zero waste techniques*, here are the steps to make it:

Table 1 Steps to make buffalo head accessories

No	Picture	Information
1.		<p>The first thing that needs to be done is to prepare the tools and materials. The tools used are cutting, knives, glue guns, rulers, pencils, paint sprayers, and brushes. In the manufacture of these accessories, most of them use waste materials from production such as styrofoam waste, used beads, <i>tinners</i>, leftover paint (coating paint, oil paint), leftover wire, leftover glue (wood glue, yellow glue), and leftover tape.</p>
2.		<p>After preparing the tools and materials, the next step is to make a pattern on the styrofoam waste according to the design.</p>
3.		<p>The next step, cut the styrofoam waste according to the pattern using a knife.</p>
4.		<p>After getting the desired pieces, glue the styrofoam waste using glue gun so that it forms a skeleton. Wire the frame with the aim of making the styrofoam easier to shape and stronger when used.</p>
5.		<p>The styrofoam waste that has been put together and shaped in such a way is then seen and tried to see if it is suitable and can be worn on the head</p>
6.		<p>After getting the appropriate frame, the next step is to paint the frame by mixing wood glue with</p>

		<p>coating paint, this is so that the paint will adhere perfectly to the styrofoam material. The next step is to dry the skeleton and repeat the above step twice.</p>
7.		<p>Once the skeleton is dry, coat the horns of the accessories with ribbon until they are completely sealed.</p>
8.		<p>The next step is to paint the outermost layer of the accessories</p>
9.		<p>The last step is to attach the used beads to the accessories until they get the desired shape.</p>
10		<p>The finished product of buffalo head accessories by applying <i>the zero waste</i> technique, namely on the main material of <i>styrofoam waste</i>.</p>

C. Dissemination of Works

1. Selected Publication Type

The type of publication chosen to display this work is a fashion show. The fashion show has the theme of Bhumibrama which is inspired by life around Mount Bromo. The performance was held in the courtyard of the Unesa rectorate at night.

Figure 4 Yard of Rektorat UNESA

Figure 5 Creation Show UNESA 2023

Figure.6 Instagram Creation Show UNESA 2023

In addition to using the type of publication in the form of fashion shows, publications are also carried out through social media, namely Instagram. Social media publications are carried out using the official Instagram platform of the title of creation, namely the title of Unesa. It is hoped that by choosing social media publications, it can reach a wider audience and make people more crowded to come to the performance.

2. Concept of Presentation of Work

The concept of the performance chosen by the Unan-Unan studio is to show a tron video depicting a husband and wife who are affected by a disaster and beg their ancestors to get protection and reject the army. Followed by the performance of the dance sendra which depicts the taking place of the traditional ceremony of Unan-Unan carried out by several residents and carrying offerings and buffalo heads using stretchers. The dancers entered the performance venue with a dark atmosphere and were accompanied by gamelan music and smoke relief that depicted the sacredness of the ceremony. This aims to give the audience an idea of how the atmosphere presented in the work and provide an idea of where the inspiration for making the work is obtained.

Figure 7 Creation Show of Clothing UNESA 2023

Figure 8 Performance Dance Show Traditional ceremonies of Unan-Unan

Figure 11 Performance Dance Show Traditional ceremonies of Unan-Unan

Results and Discussion

1. Description of the work

Figure 12 The work of buffalo boat accessories

a) Type of Work

The type of work made in this study is a buffalo head accessory inspired by the Unan-Unan ceremony.

b) Size

The size of these accessories is adjusted to the model's head which has a head circumference of 53 cm, a horn length of 50 cm on each side and a bead length of 30 cm – 50 cm.

Figure 13 The result is a buffalo head shaped accessory

c) Structure of the shape

This head accessory is inspired by the buffalo head in the Unan-Unan offering. These accessories are dominated by the shape of their horns. The horns are made to face the front with the same size between the right and left, which is 50 cm. Equipped with beaded decorations depicting flower arrangements from the offering. Accessories are made with *zero waste* techniques by utilizing leftover production materials. The main material used is *styrofoam* waste, placed as the main skeleton to form the head and horns of the buffalo. After the frame is made using *styrofoam* waste, it is added with waste wire and wrapped in cloth and uses leftover paint as a *finish*.

d) Meaning

In the offerings of the Unan-Unan ceremony there are many types of components and one of them that inspires this accessory is the buffalo head. The head of the buffalo has a very majestic, strong, and beneficial character meaning for the life of the community. The buffalo is also believed to be the mount of Betara Yama, the god of justice and policy. In terms of color, the colors used in these accessories are red and black. Red has the meaning of love, courage, strength and creativity, while black symbolizes elegance, simplicity, eternity and mystery which is in harmony with the theme of the ceremony which is so sacred.

Discussion

The results of the work assessment carried out by one of the teaching practitioners based on the foundation of creation from the work creation methodology book on May 6, 2024, stated that:

1. Aspects of Concept and Form

Based on the concept and form aspects, the teaching practitioners stated that the work was very good and in accordance with the function and also *the moodboard*.

2. Quality Aspects of Problems and Originality

Based on the results of the assessment from fashion teaching practitioners, the quality aspect of the idea and concept is very good and has also been modified according to the inspiration image.

3. Aspects of Expression

Based on the expression asked, it is considered very good in expressing the work that has been made.

4. Skill Aspects

Based on the skill aspect, fashion teachers are considered good because they can implement inspirational images into a new work.

5. Aspects of Sensitivity and Sensibility

In terms of comfort, it is quite comfortable but you still have to use a lot of *hairclips*

6. Aspects of Form and Form of Work

Based on the assessment of the aspect of the form and form of the work, it is stated that it is very good because it can realize a work from the source of ideas. Meanwhile, regarding the assessment criteria for head accessories according to (Febrianti, W and Apriyani, D. 2023)

product validity assessment indicators include shape, size, neatness, finish, color, and compatibility resulting in the following discussions:

1. Shape

In terms of shape, it can be said that the accessories that have been made are quite by the initial design, which is to have two symmetrical horns on the right and left sides, red in color, and decorated with black beads. The main frame in the accessories utilizes *styrofoam* waste so that it looks sturdy yet still lightweight when used.

Figure 14 Comparison of design and finished work

2. Size

The size comparison between the finished product and the design is appropriate, namely it has a size that is adjusted to the head of the model with a head circumference of 53 cm, horn length of 50 cm on each side and bead length of 30 cm – 50 cm.

3. Tidiness

The finished buffalo head shape accessories are quite neat and suitable for use, it's just that the end of the head is considered inappropriate because of the lack of support wire on *the styrofoam* so that the end drops slightly and there is some glue left on the accessories.

4. Final Result

The final result of buffalo head shape accessories using *the zero waste* technique, namely by minimizing *styrofoam* waste, is considered quite in accordance with the source of ideas, designs, concepts, colors and shapes and is worthy of publication with several notes. The finished product has a shape inspired by the buffalo head on the offering. It is red and has beaded decorations on its horns. The main production material of this work is *waste styrofoam*, with some additional materials such as paint, glue, and tape.

Figure 15 The result is a buffalo head shaped accessory

5. Color

The color chosen for this work is red because it is following the source of the idea, which is the offering of Unan-Unan and has the meaning of love, courage, strength, and creativity. The finished product and design both use red but in the final result the paint that has dried turns darker so that it is not in accordance with the original design.

6. Consistency

(Apsani, 2020) (Apsani, 2020) *two peace* berupa *dress* dan *blazer* bergaya *edgy* berwarna hitam. Pada *blazer* terdapat *embroidery* berbentuk tanduk kerbau yang membuat busana dan juga aksesoris sangat selaras dan saling menunjang penampilan.

Figure 16 Harmony of accessories in the shape of a buffalo head and the clothes worn

From the above assessment, it can be concluded that the results of the assessment of the buffalo head shaped accessories are considered good, in accordance with the concept, source of ideas and suitable for use with several notes.

Conclusion

Based on the above research, the results were obtained that the creation of accessories in the form of a buffalo head by applying *the zero waste* technique has fulfilled every stage of the methodology of creating works by Husen Hendriyana. This research succeeded in creating a work of accessories in the shape of a buffalo head by utilizing *styrofoam* waste with the basis and development of previous theories. This research is an exploration and concern with the current issue, namely the accumulation of waste, especially B3 waste which is very dangerous for the lungs if not managed and utilized properly.

The results of the creation of this buffalo head shaped accessories succeeded in answering research questions, starting from the process, application to the finished product of accessories that use *the zero waste* technique. The production of fashion goods that usually use quality materials until the latest production can be produced with the main material of waste. These accessories have a selling power that is not inferior to products with expensive production and use the latest materials. By utilizing waste as the main material for production, it can also add to the uniqueness and novelty of the product so that it has added value.

In this creation, it has gone through four stages of Husein Hendriyana's theory which consists of pre-design, design, embodiment, and publication. In the pre-design stage, exploration is carried out with interviews with traditional leaders and looking for inspiration through previous sources. The *zero waste* technique is applied to the use of the main material, namely styrofoam waste which is one type of B3 waste. *Styrofoam* waste is used on the entire frame of the accessories, namely the head and horns. This material has the advantage of being light when used, easy to shape, and easy to find. The realization stage is the completion stage of the *prototype* that has been felt to be in accordance with the design and design. Accessories in the shape of a buffalo head with the source of ideas for the Unan-Unan ceremony that applies *zero waste techniques*. The results of the work were published on the 2023 BHUMIBRAMA Unesa creation title and the official social media of the Unesa creation title.

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